

Not just sightseeing but resonating: reframing the trouble with the good life in post-tourism

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Abstract

Ethical reflections on the relationship between tourism and the good life remain underexplored, particularly in the context of post-tourism's fragmented and accelerated practices. While tourism's negative impacts often overshadow its potential contributions to the good life, the absence of a clear *telos* or internal good—in the Aristotelian-MacIntyrean sense—in tourism practice complicates this evaluation. How, then, can tourism practice's contribution to the good life be assessed? This paper interrogates this issue by comparing two frameworks. Unlike Dean MacCannell's approach, which argues that the practice of sightseeing embodies the good common to all tourism and its potential social benefits lie in the tourist's virtuous capacities, this work proposes that Hartmut Rosa's concept of resonance may offer an alternative foundation for a critique of the good life in tourism. This approach shifts the ethical focus from the tourist to the social and cultural dynamics of acceleration that shape contemporary tourism.

Keywords: ethics of tourism, good life, post-tourism, resonance, sightseeing, tourism

Introduction: The relationship between the good life and social practices

In an ethically pluralistic context, where each person believes they have the right to choose their own model of the good life, it is difficult to establish universal criteria for its fulfilment. This is because there is no common *telos* or a common good for all humanity. Consequently, any philosophical perspective advocating for a particular conception

of the good life risks being perceived not only as unappealing but even as threatening (Sandel, 2009: 242, 243).

However, while this reluctance is reasonable when attempting to link the good life to society as a whole, it weakens when it is confined to the realm of social practices. The foundations proposed by MacIntyre's neo-Aristotelian approach are particularly illustrative of this perspective. In contrast to the difficulty of linking the good life to a unified conception of the *telos* of humanity, there is a close and undeniable relationship between the good life and the end inherent in each social practice, which is defined as:

any coherent and complex form of socially established cooperative human activity through which goods internal to that form of activity are realized in the course of trying to achieve those standards of excellence which are appropriate to, and partially definitive of, that form of activity, with the result that human powers to achieve excellence, and human conceptions of the ends and goods involved, are systematically extended. (MacIntyre, 2007: 187)

This approach is highly useful for understanding the important relationship between virtue and social practices across various dimensions. Firstly, anyone who wishes to attain the *telos* of each social practice, which MacIntyre refers to as the internal good, knows that they must cultivate certain virtues that enable them to achieve it: 'A virtue is an acquired human quality the possession and exercise of which tends to enable us to achieve those goods which are internal to practices and the lack of which effectively prevents us from achieving any such goods' (MacIntyre, 2007: 191). This example is quite clear in this regard: 'If, on starting to play baseball, I do not accept that others know better than I when to throw a fast ball and when not, I will never learn to appreciate good pitching let alone to pitch' (MacIntyre, 2007: 190).

Secondly, the virtue or the pursuit of excellence inherent in the attainment of internal goods serves as an ethical safeguard against the problems generated by the common orientation of capitalist economic institutions towards external goods in social practices, particularly in relation to money (MacIntyre, 2007: 197).

Thirdly, the implications of cultivating virtues are not confined to the sphere of social practices and the attainment of their internal goods. Searching for a conception of the good also helps us to overcome risks, dangers, temptations, and distractions. In this sense, this quest 'is always an education both as to the character of that which is sought and in self-knowledge' (MacIntyre, 2007: 219).

What happens, however, when the evolution of a complex social practice such as tourism makes it difficult to reach agreement on what constitutes its internal good? In what follows, firstly, I will frame this problem as a starting point for arguing the need to explore new ethical frameworks for thinking about the good life in tourism. Secondly, I will examine the ethical proposal formulated by MacCannell. His attempt to attribute a common purpose to the practice of sightseeing arguably represents the most significant effort to recover a sense of unity within the complexity of tourism. However, reducing the responsibility of addressing tourism's ethical challenges to the virtuous capacity to control the desire for enjoyment generated by the tourism system may ultimately prove limiting. In response to this approach, I will turn to Hartmut Rosa's critical theory of resonance. The aim is to explore how resonance might contribute to the evaluation of the

good life in tourism in a non-paternalistic way, by taking into account the socioeconomic structures that accelerate tourism and the cultural tendency that drives it towards the continual making-available of the world.

The good life and the social practice of tourism: Framing the trouble

Intuitively, these coordinates can also be seen as highly valuable for considering how tourism might contribute to the good life. By cultivating virtues to achieve tourism's inherent purpose, we gain a mechanism to counteract economistic logics—often focused on the pursuit of external goods—while fostering holistic personal growth. Developing virtues through engagement in social practices enhances our understanding of the good we seek to achieve, deepening our appreciation of its importance and its connection to a fully realised human life. Moreover, striving for the good encourages self-awareness by compelling us to confront our limitations, challenges, and distractions, helping us to better recognise our inclinations, weaknesses, and strengths as we progress towards our goals.

However, when we look at tourism, we encounter a much more complex situation regarding its purpose or *telos*, which serves as the foundation for building the good life around social practices. Both due to the need to gather statistics related to mobility in general and the economistic interest in promoting tourism growth, tourism practice has a strongly formal component, closely tied to travel, within which almost any purpose can fit. The UN Tourism—the United Nations agency responsible for tourism, composed largely of companies with economic interests in the sector—defines a visitor as ‘a traveller taking a trip to a main destination outside his/her usual environment, for less than a year, for any main purpose (business, leisure or other personal purpose) other than to be employed by a resident entity in the country or place visited. A visitor (domestic, inbound or outbound) is classified as a tourist (or overnight visitor), if his/her trip includes an overnight stay, or as a same-day visitor (or excursionist) otherwise’ (UN Tourism, 2024). In this context, a characteristic that hinders the recognition of a clear internal good in tourism is that this activity is often offered as a conglomerate of practices. As van der Duim and Spaargaren point out in *The Relevance of Practice Theories for Tourism Research* (Lamers et al., 2017), activities such as being transported by boat, dining, and photographing polar bears are distinct and autonomous elements of touristic practices, which may or may not be coordinated by various organisations (Lamers et al., 2017: 62). Another difficulty in defining a common objective within tourist practice is also evident in the way tourists often resist normative ideas about how tourism should be done. This is clearly illustrated when tourists stray from organised tours to engage in alternative forms of travel, much like how, as Edensor suggests, following Michel de Certeau, pedestrians momentarily subvert the intended use of public space by employing tactics that reframe and reappropriate it with alternative meanings (Edensor, 2001: 76).

Nonetheless, the challenge of characterising tourism as a social practice in ethical terms is undoubtedly shaped by the post-Fordist economic dynamics that were progressively introduced from the 1970s onwards to address Fordism.

Post-Fordism has impacted tourism by diluting one of the defining features of a social practice: cooperation. As an economic strategy, it is based primarily on geographic expansion, space-time compression, significant technological innovations, flexibility in production and services, and a continuous dynamic of ‘creative destruction’, a constant search for new market niches to accelerate the turnover time of capital and thereby address the capital accumulation crises produced by Fordism (Harvey, 1990: 145, 156, 339). These tendencies have fuelled ‘de-differentiation’ processes (Urry and Larsen, 2011: 115) that seriously undermine the analytical potential of understanding tourism through structural differentiation patterns, in the sense of ‘touristic times and spaces’ that are separated as organised systems distinct from others, with their own rules and dynamics. As Urry notes (2008: xiv): there has been ‘an “implosion of tourism” into a wide range of other systems such as shopping, entertainment, migration, sport, leisure, friend-ship, business, conferences, sex, family life, etc’.

The fact that new patterns of production and consumption have rendered tourism a diffuse concept and an overly fragmented social practice was clearly highlighted by Chris Rojek and John Urry in *Touring Cultures: Transformations of Travel and Theory* (Rojek and Urry, 1997). By arguing that the traditional idea of a tourist culture existing in clear contrast to the rest of society has become implausible (Rojek and Urry, 1997: 11), they raised fundamental questions to delineate the social practice of tourism and its consequences for the good life: ‘We will begin by interrogating the very category of ‘tourism’. Is there such an entity? Does the term serve to demarcate a usefully distinct sphere of social practice? Where does tourism end and leisure or culture or hobbying and strolling begin?’ (Rojek and Urry, 1997: 1). It is therefore unsurprising that Urry proposed that we are witnessing ‘the end of “tourism” *per se*’ (Urry, 2008: xiv).

With this postmodern approach, which differs from modern approaches precisely by denying the existence of a recognisable internal good in tourism, Urry was not aiming to deny something as evident as the continued presence of tourism today, given its prevalence in contemporary language. What this posttourist position highlights is the need to move towards new paradigms to understand it more appropriately (Urry, 2008: xiv); an approach with ethical implications that David Fennell has recognised well. From the classical ethical paradigm, it is unquestionable that tourism requires virtues to develop justly and to contribute to the good life of its participants and those affected. However, it is also true that the sociocultural dynamics of tourism mean that a virtue ethics associated with the practice of tourism tends to be regarded as overly vague. If the end of tourism is unclear, it does not seem easy to deduce what virtues should be considered inherent to the practice of tourism, which would enable it to achieve its good, and how those virtues should be understood in different situations (Fennell, 2006: 74). The solution proposed by Jamal from the paradigm of virtue is that this must be discussed on a case-by-case basis. Since ‘good tourism’ is the tourism that achieves its end, those involved in tourism must make the effort to cultivate specific virtues, depending on the ends of tourism, which differs from that of other destinations (Jamal, 2004: 544).

In this text, I aim to introduce a way to justify how it is indeed possible to establish a common criterion for evaluating the good life in tourism. To this end, I draw on a framework for ethics proposed by Fennell. The difficulties in defining a more or less recognisable good in tourism reveal the challenge faced by tourism ethics:

understanding that tourism is not an activity that can be controlled, that its participants are not formally coordinated, nor are they coordinated to achieve agreed-upon ends (Fennell, 2006: 7). It is, therefore, an ethical basis that addresses these characteristics, generated not only by cultural motivations but also by the conditions imposed by the economic system—which have turned tourism into ‘runaway tourism’ (Tribe, 2009: 4)—that I intend to explore here.

To take this step, I will begin by briefly analysing the ethical approach proposed by Dean MacCannell for tourism. As Habermas suggests for any theoretical discussion on society, it is always beneficial to attempt to adopt, clarify, critique, and further develop the aims of earlier theoretical traditions (Habermas, 1984: 140). Amid all the debates about the challenges of recognising a common good in tourism, MacCannell addresses the question of the good life in tourism by linking virtue to a practice he identifies as practically universal: the sightseeing.

The ethics of sightseeing: An approach to the good life in tourism

MacCannell is a critical theorist who has provided valuable tools for thinking about and discussing the function and risks of tourism in our societies. In his canonical work, *The Tourist: A New Theory of the Leisure Class* (MacCannell, 1999), MacCannell employs a powerful approach based on the third-person perspective to analyse the social structures of alienation that drive individuals to seek authenticity—perhaps a longing for a premodern world—through tourism. This would help to explain the tendency, for instance, to ‘museify’ the pre-modern, to revere traditional music, or to frequently use language in tourism that exalts authenticity, as in references to the ‘typical village’.

Although his earlier approach to the dialectics of alienation already demonstrated, to some extent, a particular concern with tourist behaviour, it is in his later ethical works that MacCannell's critique of tourism places significant emphasis on the first-person perspective. His proposal for an approach to the good life indeed acknowledges the need to distance itself from positivist approaches in tourism research, which are primarily focused on quantitative methods to maintain a form of axiological neutrality: ‘Tourism statistics usually do not distinguish between a trip to a trade show (or a family visit) versus travel for the sole purpose of enjoying a destination’s beauty, culture, and amenities’ (MacCannell, 2011: 3–4). In contrast to the lack of a clear end implied by the wide variety of practices associated with tourism, MacCannell argues that sightseeing has an unequivocal one:

[. . .]Still I privileged sightseeing over all other tourist activities and continue to do so. Why? I might appeal to logic by noting that sightseeing is embedded in every other thing tourists do (horseback riding, family visits, mountain climbing, picnicking, etc.) but not vice versa. Ipso facto, this makes sightseeing both an end in itself and the singular supplement to everything else tourists do. I might attempt to argue statistically, that more tourists go sightseeing than any other type of tourist activity. Even if these propositions could be proven, I am disinclined to seek refuge in logic or statistics. My reasoning: sightseeing involves the whole person, mind and body, being and existence. It is about the person’s connection, or lack of connection, to

nature, heritage, other human beings, and especially, their own psyches. It is the one activity that any tourist can enjoy, old and young, the fit and the infirm, women and men, from every nation and class. The other tourist activities may have their own distinctive qualities, but none are more totalizing than sightseeing. (MacCannell, 2011: 42)

While MacCannell's focus on organised authenticity aligned him with the early theorists who sought to analyse the structures through which the 'deeper' meanings of modern tourism could be uncovered, his approach to sightseeing represents a critique of the good life that seeks to integrate post-tourism dynamics. The ethics of sightseeing aims to be relevant for the approaches emerging in the second wave of tourism studies, which advocate the importance of the socio-psychological dimension and view tourism fundamentally as a subfield of entertainment, a source of relaxation, and personal enjoyment (MacCannell, 2011: 210).

The current importance of this approach —focused more on the tourist subject than on the structures that shape them— becomes evident when considering the risks inherent in the tourist gaze described by John Urry, arguably one of the leading figures of the second wave of tourism studies. One of the issues we face is tourism's powerful ability to dehumanise the world through the construction of the *other*, which occurs via the tourist gaze. This concept refers to a process in which 'places are chosen to be gazed upon because there is anticipation, especially through daydreaming and fantasy, of intense pleasures, either on a, different scale or involving different senses from those customarily encountered' (Urry, 1990: 3). Since the gaze is indeed socially organised and systematised, shaped by institutions and professionals 'through a variety of non-tourist practices, such as film, tv, literature, magazines, records and videos, which construct and reinforce that gaze' (Urry, 1990: 3), there is always the risk that the resources we rely on to connect with otherness may be suppressed, reducing its image to something merely flat and functional. The tourist gaze can diminish the depths of the other to a compact, manageable thing, neither alive nor dead, located somewhere, thus hindering an understanding of the other as a being like ourselves, with depth, dimension, internal forces, and invisible feelings. This is perhaps the least ethical form of consciousness fostered by the apparatus of contemporary tourism (MacCannell, 2011: 195).

To address these circumstances, MacCannell introduces the notion of a 'second gaze', drawing on the Lacanian insight that the contemporary imperative to 'Enjoy!' may be more damaging to the subject than previous regimes of repression based on prohibition ('you must not'), without thereby implying the presence of an all-powerful external gaze. The second gaze builds on Urry's concept of the first gaze, emphasising the ethical potential inherent in the tourist gaze. Rather than assuming an all-powerful, objectifying gaze, the second gaze acknowledges that precisely the fact that the tourist may become caught, manipulated, and captive within the field of vision is what prompts them to interrogate their own desire. The moment the tourist attraction appears to return the gaze signals MacCannell's concern with the psychoanalytic presuppositions underlying desire: how the subject navigates or sublimates this desire is crucial to the ethical predispositions of individual tourists and the various social practices in which they participate.

Consequently, for MacCannell, the transformative potential and responsibility of the tourist in engaging with the symbols that give meaning to attractions represent one of the key avenues for transformation within tourism: ‘The second gaze turns back onto the gazing subject ethical responsibility for constructing its own existence. It refuses to leave this construction to the corporation, the state, and the apparatus of tourist representation’ (MacCannell, 2011: 210). Here lies the great hope for contributing to the good life that MacCannell identifies in sightseeing. As Welten (2014) highlights, MacCannell, in his concept of the second gaze, emphasises the ethical self-reflective capacity of tourists — the ability to engage their ethical consciousness and self-construction— rather than merely reinforcing consumerist representations of the world.

For instance, the Statue of Liberty can be seen merely as a magnificent object, a toptier tourist attraction that must be visited, or alternatively, as a symbol of freedom. However, it is not freedom itself. This attraction demonstrates the extent to which symbols are regarded as aggregative magnets of meaning. Like any attraction, it represents a belief, or set of beliefs, shared within a human community (MacCannell, 2011: 58), and precisely for this reason, it is to be expected that relationships in tourism are not always necessarily one-directional. According to MacCannell, the Statue of Liberty can also pose a question to the tourist: ‘What exactly have you done lately to advance the cause of liberty?’.

It is a step forward in aligning ethics with the realities of tourism that the ethics of sightseeing incorporates the dynamics of pleasure-seeking and the superficiality of tourism from the consumer’s perspective, which postmodern approaches to tourism highlight as essential to consider, yet without abandoning the question of tourism’s ultimate good. No matter how superficial your intentions may be practising tourism, sightseeing always holds the possibility for the attraction to challenge you ethically. In this way, the ethics of sightseeing certainly adopt a more formal, or perhaps less substantive, ethical perspective, enabling it to transcend the problematic approach based on authenticity that MacCannell presents in *The Tourist*. The pursuit of authenticity is not necessarily a goal that must always align with the current purposes of tourism. As reflected in the idea that tourism fundamentally stems from the ‘contact between the tourist and a true attraction’ (MacCannell, 1999: 156, 157), authenticity carries a deeply static anthropological characterisation, offering little as a reference point for critiquing a complex and ever-changing social practice such as tourism.

The ethics of sightseeing is, therefore, a proposal with commendable intentions as a critique of the good life in tourism, justified by a specific internal good —sightseeing— attributed to tourism. Nonetheless, it is not without its challenges or inherent limitations. From my point of view, the excessive responsibility placed on the tourist is perhaps the main one. The ethics of sightseeing practically limits the ethical potential to view tourism’s transformative power as merely a matter of tourists’ virtue (MacCannell, 2011: 47). The attribution of responsibility for realising the full potential of sightseeing to the tourist becomes evident when MacCannell observes that tourists often seem unwilling to ‘add ethical burdens to our already heavy vacation baggage’ (MacCannell, 2011: 46): ‘Does the tourist relate to the other as an end in itself, something to be enjoyed even if it serves no purpose?’ or ‘Does the tourist relate to the other as a means to an end?’ (MacCannell, 2011: 10).

In summary, MacCannell attributes tourism's transformative potential to the desire to establish a connection with someone or with the 'other', as represented or embodied in an attraction. This connection demands an effort that not all tourists are willing to make, and therefore, not all succeed in fulfilling the good of tourism practice (MacCannell, 2011: 7). To critique the establishment of relationships of domination rather than connection with 'the other', MacCannell argues it would suffice to emphasise an Aristotelian 'ethics of sightseeing [that] requires an awareness as such of the imaginary mediation of self and other' (MacCannell, 2011: 190).

This proposal is based on an idea that remains central throughout MacCannell's thinking (MacCannell, 1999: 202): 'the dividing line between structure genuine and spurious is the realm of the commercial'. There is something fundamental in the practice of tourism, even beyond spurious commercial interests: 'Sightseeing is tourism's default. It is the only thing tourists can do at every waking moment independent of their other reasons to travel. It is the only thing tourists are supposed to be good at. Also sightseeing, as an end in itself, is privileged among tourist pursuits by unique ethical contours and its potential to clarify ethics in general' (MacCannell, 2011: 42). Nonetheless, in contradiction to this narrowing of boundaries to the tourist and their virtues, MacCannell also implicitly acknowledges aspects that invite further reflection on the good life in tourism from other perspectives. MacCannell recognises that the relationship between the tourist and the attraction in sightseeing depends on many forms of relating to the world beyond: the sightseeing is indeed about 'the person's connection, or lack of connection, to nature, heritage, other human beings, and especially, their own psyches' (MacCannell, 2011: 42).

To the extent that cultural, social, and economic factors are recognised as always already shaping any form of relating, it becomes justifiable to seek horizons for an ethical critique where the good life in tourism does not rely solely on tourists, their virtues, or their consciousness, but rather on how these factors shape their ways of relating to the objective, subjective, and intersubjective dimensions of the world. With this approach, drawing on Hartmut Rosa's critical theory, I aim to broaden the scope of the critique of the good life in tourism to encompass a wider spectrum of activities classified as tourism. I propose to extend the reflection on the good life beyond the parameters of the tourist and an attraction, as well as to all those affected by tourism. To this end, I will begin by justifying the existence of a cultural trait often presented as a correlate of social conditions of acceleration, which have characterised tourism almost universally from its inception to the present day. This trait, despite being conceived as positive, represents one of the obstacles to achieving the good life: the continual making of the world available.

The impact of social acceleration on the good life in tourism

Hartmut Rosa has become one of the most prominent critical theorists of the latest—for some, the fourth—generation within the Frankfurt School's German tradition, based on his analysis of social acceleration. This object of study converges with a key premise

shared by the diverse works that have emerged within this tradition, regardless of the extent to which individual members of this generation were influenced by Marx: the social conditions that give rise to the pathologies of capitalist societies are structurally characterised by their capacity to obscure precisely those realities most deserving of sharp public criticism (Honneth, 2009).

The problematic nature of acceleration can be discerned from his basic definition, formulated in his early works, which already represents a substantive advance in the field of the sociology of time: ‘acceleration can first be defined in line with its basic physical meaning as an increase in quantity per unit of time’ (Rosa, 1999: 390). However, according to Rosa’s model, the challenge with acceleration—which often remains unchallenged—becomes apparent when we consider that we are not dealing with a single phenomenon of acceleration, but rather with the relationship between three types: technological acceleration, the acceleration of the rate of social change, and the acceleration of the pace of life. Contrary to expectations, technological acceleration does not result in social time savings. Alongside the instability of social practices—which typically accompany technological acceleration—there is a systematic increase in the pace of life, which neither technological advances nor higher rates of social change are able to resolve. On the contrary, a kind of vicious cycle emerges between these three phenomena, reinforcing the tendency towards further acceleration (Rosa, 2010).

One reason this occurs is that, as Rosa’s very definition of acceleration shows, increase is one of its inherent characteristics. As Harvey noted, particularly in relation to the economy, the logic of ever-increasing acceleration is closely linked to the economic system. This association is particularly clear in the tourism boom of the 1970s, marking the beginning of a phase that underscores the negative impact of tourism on the good life of its participants: the precautionary phase (Butler, 1980; Jafari, 2001; Turner and Ash, 1975).

Since the 1970s, tourism has developed impressively due to the ‘coercive laws of market competition’ (Harvey, 1990: 180). The logic of acceleration in capital turnover, recognisable in the well-known Marxist formula M-C-M’ (Money-Commodity-Money plus profit), which refers to the circuit of circulation and accumulation of value in an economy through the buying and selling of commodities (Marx, 1906: 163–173), has found in tourism a perfect ally. What better than tourism, with its great capacity to set in motion the ‘golden egg’ of a mobile gross domestic product (Munt, 1994: 49), to overcome the rigidities of the Fordist model? The answer is ‘nothing’ if we indeed consider that ‘capital is value only when it is in motion’ (Harvey, 2006: 132) and that its acceleration is key to increasing the ‘rate of profit’ (Harvey, 2006: 86) necessary for continued growth. This is a desirable horizon for capitalists who argue that ‘crises are caused by a lack of growth’ (Harvey, 1990: 180). This logic of acceleration, driven by competition for resources, even permeates sustainable tourism initiatives, as a consequence of the widespread tendency to view ‘a truly competitive tourism destination as one with the ability to increase tourism expenditure’ (Ritchie and Crouch, 2003: 2).

Technological acceleration undoubtedly plays an important role on the supply side of tourism, but historically it has also been a driving force behind its consumption. Indeed, one could argue that acceleration is key to comprehending the sociohistorical nature of modern tourism, beyond essentialist approaches. As Joseph Krippendorf pointed out in

The Holiday Makers (Krippendorf, 1987), the force driving millions of people away from their homes today is less a matter of an inherent urge in human nature to travel: ‘The travel needs of the modern age have been largely created by society and shaped by everyday life. People go away because they no longer feel happy where they are, where they work, where they live. In order to be able to carry on, they urgently need a temporary refuge from the burdens imposed by the everyday work, home and leisure scene’ (Krippendorf, 1987: XIV).

According to Rosa’s social acceleration theory, the drive for growth necessitates a third form of acceleration, which is arguably key to understanding the ideas advanced by post-tourism theories and, more broadly, to appreciating the antinomies inherent in attempts to develop a critical ethical framework for tourism-related social practices: the acceleration of the rate of social change. Acceleration not only promotes the global spread of a stable social practice, but also reduces the stability of social practices, or in other words, accelerates their rate of social change (Rosa, 2010: 33).

This type of social acceleration has accompanied modern tourism since its inception. Thomas Cook’s success was not solely due to his adaptation to the technological acceleration represented by the train, but also to his introduction of innovative cultural practices such as renting trains from railway companies to organise leisure excursions. Since then, the same continuous innovation that generates the acceleration of social change has been a key element in the evolution of tourism, to the extent that it has contributed to the decline of one of the modern forms of organising it: the package holiday. Especially since the 1970s, with the onset of disorganised capitalism (Lash and Urry, 1994: 253), the proliferation of new forms of tourism have emerged, creating challenges in differentiating tourism from leisure, culture, education, sports, or hobbies, among others (Lash and Urry, 1994: 274).

The phenomenon of the acceleration of social change highlights a close connection between socioeconomic coercion to accelerate and the cultural tendency to make the world controllable —available, accessible, and attainable— (Rosa, 2018), a relationship that is highly useful for understanding the evolution of tourism. The drive to make the world controllable was already evident in Thomas Cook’s landmark achievement in tourism. He did not conceive of tourism merely as a business offering opportunities for travel and enjoyment but as an endeavour with serious cultural, social, and political implications, ultimately aimed at making the world accessible and available to all:

For Thomas Cook, the founder of modern tourism, this would certainly have been a wish come true. For him, accessibility to the world, its natures, histories, peoples and cultures was an urgently needed resource for modern individuals and nations; tourism was a route to enlightenment in a globalising world. For Cook extending the numbers and sorts of people who had access to travel and a world beyond their home was seen as a positive, democratising project that could produce a more evenly educated civil society with more equal life chances and a society more tolerant of others; a civil society that could more easily take part in national life and a more peaceful cooperative world. (Franklin, 2003: 22)

This same tendency to make the entire world available for tourism remains present today, both in its physical and value dimensions, almost always driven by the economy’s search

to create new ‘market niches’ (Harvey, 1990: 145). The easiest way to grasp this cultural tendency is to pay attention to the global expansion of tourism. As Lovelock and Lovelock (2013: 3) propose, the fact that tourism has become ‘almost ubiquitous’ constitutes a global ethical problem. However, this tendency also commonly manifests itself in the practice of tourism. The idea that tourism is based on making the world available can be recognised in tourists’ desire to move from the front region to the back, as observed by MacCannell, without necessarily interpreting this action as a quest for authenticity, as suggested by MacCannell’s theory of organised authenticity, analysed earlier in the third section. Dutch writer Ilja Leonard Pfeijffer (2021) also captures the physical significance of this trend in his book *Grand Hotel Europa*, questioning why we want to see the Mona Lisa in a museum so crowded with tourists that it barely allows us to view the painting. One might question whether it’s really about the painting itself. What we are undoubtedly seeking is the sense of proximity, the unique experience that provides us with a story, preferably sealed with a selfie (Pfeijffer, 2021: 128, 129). Viewing tourism through the lens of ‘making the world available’ also allows us to consider how the cultural correlation necessary for acceleration and growth orientation leads to the colonisation of previously non-touristic spheres of value, as vividly illustrated by the processes of touristification of jobs (López-González, 2023) embodied in practices such as bleisure and workation.

A reading from Rosa’s critical theory on how tourism is coercively shaped by social acceleration, growth, and the need for continuous innovation, while also manifesting a cultural counterpart that seeks to make everything available, highlights a risk in the conditions for achieving the good life: alienation. Despite the challenges in defining such a frequently used term in critical theory since Marx, Rosa’s proposal is, one might say, quite precise: alienation consists in the development of relationships without relation [*eine Beziehung der Beziehungslosigkeit*] (Rosa, 2019: 19).

This type of critique allows us to raise an ethically relevant issue that the ethics of sightseeing itself already seeks to address: alienation is not an irreversible state. The diagnosis of authenticity lent itself to a certain deterministic reading of the good life in tourism by attributing strong significance to a structuralist view of the tourist experience, where tourists almost universally seek authenticity and are guided by social and cultural structures towards certain behaviours. Adopting this viewpoint carried the risk of endorsing a form of determinism —a denial of freedom— that would limit tourism critique by suggesting that the internalisation of domination reaches its peak and perfection in modern tourism, to the extent that it demonstrates that there are no better slaves than happy slaves (Aramberri, 2010). In contrast, the ethics of sightseeing seeks to transcend the determinist nature of tourism logic, albeit by placing considerable emphasis on the individual and on pleasure, elements highly regarded in post-tourist perspectives. According to MacCannell, his ethics of sightseeing recognises that it is possible to break free from the ‘iron circle of narcissistic determinism’ (MacCannell, 2011: 200), particularly through the ethical character embodied in the second tourist gaze—that moment when the tourist is addressed—where the virtues of the tourist play a crucial role.

Perhaps the most significant innovation introduced by drawing on the critical theory of resonance is that it allows us to suggest that overcoming alienation in tourism cannot rest solely on the virtue of the tourist. The structural compulsion to accelerate, grow, and

innovate, which operates forcefully within tourism, is not a dynamic that exists entirely outside the society that both enjoys and is impacted by it, and thus does not strictly determine it. It would always be possible to alter these dynamics; however, a critique from a purely subject-centred framework is insufficient to do so. According to Rosa's theory, alienation in tourism is not merely a socioeconomic issue, nor simply a fault in the way the tourist approaches their activity. Alienation arises because the compulsion to accelerate, grow, and innovate, together with its cultural counterpart of making everything available, establishes a misguided way of relating to the world.

By focusing on the mode of relating, resonance model helps avoid attributing the causes of alienation to disorders in the subject's relations [*Beziehungsstörungen der Subjekte*] through an emphasis on the tourist, an approach that both post-tourist sociological perspectives and the ethics of sightseeing can so readily encourage. In contrast to the subjectivist reductionism to which these approaches also tend, the critical theory of resonance shifts the focus to the conditions influencing modes of relating. This does not mean that the subject—the tourist—is overlooked; rather, it recognises the importance of socio-structural and cultural aspects that shape how those involved in or affected by tourism relate. These aspects precede individual consciousness (Rosa, 2016: 66) and form part of the connection among of objective, social, and subjective dimensions (Rosa, 2016: 69) that shape our *Weltbeziehung*—our way of relating to the world—in which everyone is always already embedded. From this perspective, the criteria for the good life in tourism also should consider relationships with nature, with other people, and with oneself (Haker, 2019: 37).

The ethics of resonance: An approach to the good life in post-tourism

The ethical criterion Rosa proposes in response to the problematic mode of relating to the world—which characterises tourism—is resonance, a concept deeply rooted in the phenomenological tradition and founded on the premise that subjects are invariably 'situated within the world', inherently immersed in and connected to it as a whole. As a metacrite- rion for the good life, which emphasises the procedural moments of resonance enabling non-alienating relationships with the world, resonance is a way of relating in which there is an affective moment where one part of the relationship feels touched. This moment is essential for another step in resonance to occur: at least one party is moved—*emovere*—to reach out in search of the Other within the relationship, allowing participants to ultimately emerge transformed (Rosa, 2018b: 37–47). The relevance of the opposite of resonance—namely, mute or alienated relationships with the world—can be illustrated graphically through the behaviour of two tuning forks in the physical process of resonance (Rosa, 2016: 212). When relationships are marked by the coercion to accelerate, grow, and innovate, as well as to make the world available, there is a risk of distancing ourselves from a mode of relating in which, as with two tuning forks in a process of resonance, both parties vibrate, feel touched, and undergo transformation.

It would be a foolish idea [*eine törichte Idee*] to think that tourism could rely on a critical theory of resonance to reject all alienating and non-resonant relationships.

Achievements in technology, science, economics and administration, politics, and law have also created the conditions of (im)possibility for establishing resonant relationships, and tourism is no exception. The problem arises when the way we engage in tourism undermines the capacity for the formation and/or maintenance [*Ausbildung und/oder Aufrechterhaltung*] of axes of resonance (Rosa, 2016: 122). From this perspective, a resonance-based approach inevitably demands political struggle for meaningful transformation. Practically speaking, it leads to recommending policies aimed at preserving the fundamental conditions for resonance, which can contribute to developing any model of the good life for those who both enjoy and are affected by tourism, structured around three key axes: a horizontal axis, based on social relationships with other people; a diagonal axis, accounting for relationships with objects; and a vertical axis, which reflects relationships with the world as a whole (Rosa, 2016: 331–514).

From an explanatory perspective, these levels allow for the coherent consolidation of different types of tourism experiences in a non-essentialist manner, grounded in the fundamental idea that good tourism is characterised by affective, active, and transformative relationships —among participants, with oneself, and with the objective world, such as nature. However, and most importantly from Rosa’s perspective, the process that characterises resonance is not merely explanatory but also offers criteria for evaluating the good life across the three axes of resonance. Here, some examples are proposed to demonstrate their functionality in the ethical critique of tourism, encompassing both tourists and those affected by tourism.

Tourism relationships on the horizontal axis are currently essential for evaluating interactions between tourists and local populations. A form of tourism that turns a deaf ear to what is happening at a destination, that does not allow those involved to feel touched by the issues faced by its inhabitants, may lack the minimal foundations necessary for the development of any good life project. This is, unfortunately, as noted earlier, a tendency fostered by the tourism system, which seeks to ensure that the tourist does not ‘pack’ any ‘duties’ in their luggage (MacCannell, 2011: 46).

The vertical axis of resonance refers to the subject’s relationship with something transcends them, that profoundly interpellates them, and by which they are affectively moved. In this sense, resonance provides a framework for evaluating various tourism-related relationships in which this axis may be at work. For example, the careful planning of such a journey does not necessarily guarantee the expected outcome. Resonance, in this sense, cannot be forced; no matter how much one seeks it, it may simply not occur. Thus, if a resonant process fails to emerge, there are grounds to argue that the good attributed to a form of tourism has not been realised. The elusive nature of resonance also serves as a useful criterion for assessing how tourists may be shaped by instrumentalised discourses. A telling example is the institutional promotion of tourism under the banner of cosmopolitanism (Bianchi and Stephenson, 2014). Relationships framed by cosmopolitan ideals can only be considered resonant if local actors involved in tourism —and not just tourists— are not reduced to mere objects of a dominant cosmopolitan discourse, but instead emerge transformed by the touristic encounter.

The ethical critique of resonant relationships along the diagonal axis is also crucial for tourism. This dimension encompasses relationships with the specific materiality of the world, with things such as attractions or landscapes, whose relevance is already

emphasised by MacCannell, even though he ultimately reduces ethical relationships to the consciousness of the tourist: ‘the “other” or “otherness” involves unfamiliar geography, including different cultures, exogenous natural and historical frameworks, artificially constructed pleasure ‘islands’, such as resorts, tour boats, etc’. (MacCannell, 2012: 184).

Certainly, applying a theory of resonance to tourism must confront the challenges involved in assessing the quality of relationships that emerge across different types of tourist destinations, such as sites of collective suffering like the Auschwitz camp. It is not easy to conceive of such relationships in terms of the good life, given that these sites are not universally regarded as exemplifying it. However, such an assessment might still be justified if one considers that these experiences can enhance affective and emotional capacities, as well as the potential for personal transformation, in ways that contribute to preventing injustices of such magnitude from recurring.

In other areas of application, however, evaluating tourism through the lens of resonance appears not only appropriate but necessary. For example, sports tourism also fits into this type of experience with things, where the body is experienced as a living thing that is, as noted earlier, not only as *Körper* —material body— but as *Leib* —lived body. This dimension is also essential for evaluating the relationship tourism workers have with their own bodies. An illustrative case highlighting the importance of this dimension is that of chambermaids (Cañada, 2023). These workers face demands to work more in less time under precarious conditions, leading them to objectify their bodies, viewing them as mere tools at the employer’s disposal. This tendency even prompts some workers to resort to medication.

The mode of resonant relating at this level can also be useful for critically analysing hybrid practices, partly work-related and partly tourism-oriented, such as bleisure or workations. To the extent that, as some empirical studies suggest, ‘working from a hotel located on a paradisiacal beach can be as alienating as doing so from an office’ (Mancinelli, 2020: 15), a focus on the diagonal axis of resonance should question the quality of the relationship established with specific purposes —jobs that carry a tourism-oriented imaginary— or objects, such as technology. This approach also allows for scrutiny of the meaning and individual implications of the concept of *smart*, which emerged in the tourism sector to label the use of technologies (Tribe and Mkono, 2017).

Conclusion

This study has sought to broaden the scope of reflection on the ethical critique of tourism at a time when the conventional view of tourism as one of the most significant activities for fostering the good life worldwide (Pearce et al., 2010) is increasingly contrasted with the perception that it is also a source of obstacles to achieving any conception of the good life due to its negative impacts.

The theoretical starting point for justifying a study of this kind has been to highlight the challenges of ethically evaluating the good life in tourism. As the moral philosopher Alasdair MacIntyre, each social practice contains certain internal goods. These are precisely what give it meaning and are distinct from external goods —such as money— which could be obtained through other activities. In a sense, these goods constitute a

criterion: if they are not attained, we may say that the social practice does not deliver what is expected of it. At the same time, forging excellence by cultivating virtues through participation in social practices enhances our understanding of the internal good we pursue, enables us to attain it, and deepens our awareness of its meaning and its connection to a full and meaningful human existence.

However, when the good life in tourism is analysed from the paradigm of virtue and social practices, a crucial aspect for discussion emerges. It is no longer easy to determine the exact relationship between the good life and the inherent purpose of the tourism practice. The complexity tourism has reached in recent decades—which suggests we are now in a post-tourism phase—seems to rule out any possibility of identifying common features of tourism practice or of defining the internal goods of tourism once and for all. In response to these tendencies, which have led to the abandonment of any attempt to establish ethically grounded criteria for the good life in tourism, in this article I have proposed—drawing on Hartmut Rosa’s critical theory—that one of the most fruitful avenues for a critique of the good life in tourism should consider both the coercive dynamics of acceleration, growth, and innovation, as well as the cultural drive to make everything accessible. These are certainly characteristics of much contemporary tourism, including that described by post-tourism perspectives. Hence, at least in relation to these features, we may continue to refer to tourism as modern.

Consequently, in light of this descriptive feature of tourism, I have suggested that the ethical concept of resonance, which Rosa proposes as a criterion for evaluating the negative consequences of social acceleration, offers a way to rethink the ethical critique of the good life in tourism within what I would tentatively call an ethics of late-tourism, in order to distance itself from interpretations that associate post-tourism with an uncritical celebration of de-differentiation processes.

To substantiate the value of this proposal, I have drawn upon an analysis of MacCannell’s ethical approach to sightseeing, which argues that, even in post-touristic practices, a connection between tourism and the good life can be established by focusing on the practice of sightseeing. This is a practice with a good—to connect with the Other—that possesses several key characteristics. First, it is sufficiently formal to be applicable across all types of tourism. Second, the fulfilment of the good of sightseeing is linked to a capacity for social transformation that extends far beyond tourism itself. Third, drawing on Aristotelian ethics, MacCannell contends that the ability to achieve this good relies on tourists cultivating specific virtues.

The ethics of sightseeing certainly provides a critical framework for examining tourism’s structural role in shaping contemporary subjectivities and social relations (Nikolakakis, 2025). Nonetheless, placing the focus on the cultivation of the tourist’s virtue presents a rather limited framework for critiquing the good life in tourism. I believe this is particularly plausible when considering, as MacCannell himself emphasises, that sightseeing involves relationships not only with attractions but also with one- self, with nature and objects, and with other people. All these dimensions are always already framed within a specific social and cultural context, the course of which, naturally, does not depend solely on any single individual.

Alternatively, the concept of resonance offers the possibility of establishing a critique of the conditions for the good life without having to assume the stability of any given

tourism practice once and for all, and without placing the entire ethical responsibility solely on the tourist. Instead of taking the internal good in tourism as a reference point, an ethical critique based on the parameters of resonance focuses on the way of relating to the world in tourism, which is socially and culturally shaped by patterns of acceleration. The evaluative criteria for these relationships would then be those contained in the definition of resonance itself: a mode of relating to the world — objective, subjective, and intersubjective— characterised by a moment when the parties involved are affected, from a passive standpoint; from an active standpoint, they respond emotionally; and finally, the parties implicated in the tourist relationship are transformed.

It is important to emphasise that the development of this work has been fundamentally theoretical and has not aimed to provide concrete empirical applications or detailed practical solutions. To that end, further research within tourism ethics would be required both to critique the potential of such a model and to concretise its transformative capacity in tourism relationships. In the latter case, any approach grounded in resonance ethics for tourism must take into account that, in principle, the prescription of substantive models of the good life cannot be justified. That is to say, it would not be possible to prescribe ‘resonant tourism’ as merely another form of ethical tourism. Within the resonance ethics framework, it is not possible to dictate which experiences of resonance should occur, nor in which of its possible dimensions they must be fully developed once and for all. On the contrary, the resonance model offers a critique of the conditions of resonance. [*Resonanzverhältnisse*] (Rosa, 2016: 309).

Given that the ways of establishing resonant relationships are socio-historically contingent and therefore subject to change, it must be borne in mind that the conditions enabling them should be debated and defined within each socio-historical moment. Precisely in light of the erosion of the capacity to resonate to which tourism workers and local residents affected by tourism are so often subjected, it would be naïve to suppose that an approach based on resonance could achieve effective change if it is not channelled through—or at least kept in step with— policies that foster a less aggressive ethical mode of relating to the good life.

Finally, the fact that the concept of resonance provides a basis for developing an ethical critique addressing questions of the good life in tourism, rather than a moral critique reserved for universal normative criteria, does not mean that we must wait for the arrival of a just society, or of just tourism, to begin working towards a good life. On the contrary, perhaps changes in the way our relationships with the world are established—currently based on a questionable positive conception of the good life grounded in the imperatives to accelerate, grow, innovate, and make the world, both physically and symbolically, available for tourism— may also constitute a way to begin addressing the problem of justice (Rosa and Zaretsky, 2017).

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